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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****COMPLICATIONS AFTER SURGICAL INTERVENTION AT A
TEACHING HOSPITAL IN PAKISTAN****¹Dr. Tahura Rasul, ²Dr Tayyaba Urooj, ³Dr. Zain Ghani.**¹THQ Hospital Kunjah, Gujrat, ²Quaid-e-Azam Medical College Bahawalpur,³Services Hospital, Lahore.**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: This research work aimed to determine the complications after surgical interventions in the duration of stay in hospital in the surgical ward of a famous hospital of Lahore.

Methodology: This was an elaborate retroactive research work. This research study carried out in the Surgical Unit-4 of General Hospital, Lahore. This research work covered a duration of complete seven months from June to December of the year 2018. We reviewed the records of all the patients who faced surgical intervention in the duration of this research study about complications after surgery whose development carried out during stay in hospital. We collected the information about age of the patient, their gender, appearance at the time of operation, performed surgery, abnormalities/complications after the surgical intervention & outcome of the treatment. SPSS V. 10 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information.

Results: Total five hundred and one patients got admission in the duration of this research work. Four hundred and eleven surgeries performed in his duration. About 62.80% (n: 258) were elective & 37.20% (n: 153) were emergency methods. The most common surgery carried out in 22.40% (n: 92) patients was hernia repair, followed by surgical removal appendix in 15.60% (n: 64) & cholecystectomy in 13.20% (n: 54) patients. We documented the complications in 29.60% (n: 122) patients. The very frequent complication was after surgery pyrexia available in 18.20% (n: 75) patients, followed by nausea & vomiting after surgical intervention present in 11.60% (n: 48) patients, infection of wound was present in 11.40% (n: 47) patients and the infection of respiratory tract was present in 7% (n: 29) patients. In the duration of this research work, 0.90% (n: 4) met their death in the period after surgical intervention.

Conclusion: This research study discovered that the most common complications after surgical interventions were high fever, infection of wound, nausea, vomiting and infection of the respiratory tract. This is very important for the professionals to know about these complications as well as the management of these complications to enhance the quality of life of these patients.

Key Words: Complications, surgery, nausea, vomiting, infection, management, pyrexia, intervention, frequent, respiratory tract.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Tahura Rasul,**

THQ Hospital Kunjah, Gujrat.

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INTRODUCTION:

After operation complications can happen after any surgery and these complications will keep occurring. Surgeons can tackle these problems with their experience and wisdom [1]. Post-surgical complications are the negative outcomes as perceived by patient or surgeon [2]. These complications may occur in initial stage of surgery, or immediate duration after the surgery. This research work carried out to determine the various complications after surgical intervention in the surgical ward of the hospital so that, we can suggest effective precautions to decrease the occurrence of these complications. Adverse incidents that have relation to the procedures of care like complications after surgical intervention, may be a better calculation of the quality than rates of death or other intermediary outcomes [3].

METHODOLOGY:

In this research work, we reviewed the records of the patients who had to face elective or emergency surgical intervention in the duration of this research work. This research study started in June 2018 and finished December of the same month about the incidence of the complications after surgical intervention. The patients who got admission, but no surgical intervention carried out were not the part of this research work. We recorded the information about the age of the patient, gender, appearance at the time of operation, performed surgery, complications in the

duration after surgical intervention. SPSS V.10 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. We also noted the frequencies of the various surgeries performed & complications after surgical intervention.

RESULTS:

Total 501 patients got admission in the duration of this research study. Total four hundred and eleven surgeries performed which contained 62.8 (n: 258) elective & 37.20% (n: 153) emergency methods. The most frequent surgical intervention was repair of hernia available in 22.40% (n: 92) patients. Appendectomy carried out in 15.60% (n: 64) patients, explorative laparotomy performed in 13.60% (n: 56) patients and cholecystectomy carried out in 13.40% (n: 54) patients. Out of total fifty four cholecystectomies, 3.20% (n: 13) were open & 10% (n: 41) cholecystectomies were laparoscopic. Table-1 is describing the various surgeries performed in this research study. We found the complications in 29.60% (n: 122) patients. Majority of the complications emerged after emergency surgical interventions, 61.50% (n: 75) in comparison to the 38.50% (n: 47) in elective methods. Pyrexia was the most frequent complication after surgery present in 18.20% (n: 75) patients, followed by nausea & vomiting in 11.60% (n: 48), infection of wound in 11.40% (n: 47) patients, infection of the respiratory tract in 7% (n: 27) patients.

Table-I: Surgeries performed during research period

Operations	No	Percentage
Hernia repair	92.00	22.40
Appendectomy	64.00	15.60
Laparotomy	56.00	13.60
Cholecystectomy	54.00	13.20
Incision & Drainage	39.00	9.50
Ano-rectal surgery	33.00	8.00
Thyroidectomy	20.00	4.90
Breast Surgery	14.00	3.40
Testicular and scrotal surgery	12.00	2.90
Chest tube intubation	4.00	1.00
Splenectomy	2.00	0.50
Miscellaneous surgeries	21.00	5.10
Total	411.00	100.00

Only one patient developed fecal fistula whereas 1 patient developed dehiscence of the wound. About 0.90% (n: 4) patients met their death after the surgery in the duration of this research work. All the complications are available in Table-2. We did not observe the complication of venous thromboembolic.

Table II: Postoperative complications

Post-Operative Complications	No	Percentage
Fever	75.00	18.20
Nausea / Vomiting	48.00	11.60
Wound Infection	47.00	11.40
Respiratory tract infection	29.00	7.00
Prolonged paralytic ileus	12.00	2.90
Spinal Headache	9.00	2.20
Wound hematoma	4.00	0.90
Septicemia	3.00	0.70
Ileostomy related	2.00	0.40
Intra-abdominal bleeding	1.00	0.20
Wound Dehiscence	1.00	0.20
Faecal Fistula	1.00	0.20
Myocardial Infarction	1.00	0.20
Mortality	4.00	0.90
Miscellaneous	23.00	5.60

DISCUSSION

Careful after surgery care is very important as the before surgery preparation for a positive outcome of the operation. Incomplete can never provide the unsuitable results regardless of the surgery standard [4]. Most common complication after surgery is fever [5, 6]. In this research study, most common complication was fever present in 18.20% (n: 75) patients. Inflammatory stimulus of operation was the reason behind the fever after surgery [7, 8]. Between 2-5 days after surgery, pyrexia can be the outcome of thrombophlebitis or urinary tract infection or infection the chest & after greater than 5 days of surgery, there is possibility of the infection of wound or anastomotic breakdown [9]. A research work displayed that 26.0% patients developed fever after surgery [10]. PONV (Post-operative nausea & vomiting) are very common complication after surgery [11]. In comparison with the other complications due to surgical intervention like infection of wound, and vein thrombosis, PONV has very little importance because it is never a cause of death.

Overall occurrence of PONV is approximately 30.0% but it can be 70.0% in the patients with high risk [12]. Infection of the wound is well-recognized complication and it is also high burden of the health service [13]. It is also responsible for 38.0% NI (nosocomial infections) [14]. One research work [15] showed the rate of infection of 1.380%. After surgery pulmonary complications are very frequent & a main reason of overall perioperative morbidity as well as mortality [16, 17]. The stomach recovery took 24 to 48 hours after surgery [18]. After surgery ileus lasts greater than three days and termed as after surgery

paralytic ileus [19]. Chang [20] stated that after surgery ileus was very frequent complication, affecting 18.0% patients after the application of radical cystectomy.

Dehiscence of the wound is the acute failure of the wound. The occurrence of this complication is 2.0% & it has linked mortality of 25.0% [21]. Pavlidis [22] has concluded that wound of the abdomen cavity, dehiscence of wound occurred in eighty nine patients out of about twenty thousand patients present with main abdominal surgeries. MI (myocardial infarction) is very frequent reason of morbidity & mortality in the patients who were available with non-cardiac operations [23]. The rate of mortality among the patients with perioperative MI ranges from 36.0% to 70.0% [24, 25]. Lindenauer in his research work displayed that a large rate of after surgery MI can be restricted by the proper administration [26]. In the non-availability of the prophylaxis, venous thromboembolism rates as high as 25.0% in general surgery [27]. In USA & countries of Europe, DVT is available in over five million incidents every year, whereas PE is available in 500000 patients [28]. This is very uncommon complication in the Asians [29].

Six publications about surgery concluded an occurrence of DVT (Deep Vein Thrombosis) having a range from 3.0% to 28.0% [30-35]. A research work from Singapore displayed that out of two hundred and twenty-seven elective surgeries, only one patient developed deep vein thrombosis after surgery whereas we found no patients with pulmonary embolism or PE [36]. A research study from Japan displayed that

overall occurrence of pulmonary embolism after surgery was 0.330% & fatal pulmonary embolism was 0.080% [37]. In this research work, we did not see a single case of DVT and/or PE. It is necessary to anticipate the disease on early stage and application of the precautions must be on initial stages. In time identification with abrupt intervention is better way to decrease the rate of complications.

CONCLUSION:

There is possibility of occurrence of complications after any surgical intervention. Preoperative assessment sound surgical method and follow-up can prevent the occurrence of most of complications. It is the duty of the professionals to inform the patients about all the probable risks. Patients should get awareness about the in-time identification and discussing abnormalities. Clear & honest discourse of the goals of surgical intervention, suspicious listening to the concerns of the patient & rapid intervention when there is suspicion of the occurrence of complications.

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